

THEORETICAL ISSUES OF CONCEPT AND COMPOSITION OF TRADE CLUSTER

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Abstract. *The concept of the trade cluster as an innovative factor and its theoretical issues are considered in the article. The state of study of the concept of cluster by foreign and domestic scientists, as well as some opinions on its definition are presented. Theoretical issues about clustering are explored, and a definition of a trade cluster is developed and theoretically grounded for the first time.*

Keywords: *trade, cluster, trade cluster, material wealth, commodity, intangible wealth, financial resource, money, trade process, property rights.*

ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ВОПРОСЫ ПОНЯТИЯ И СОСТАВА ТОРГОВОГО КЛАСТЕРА

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается понятие торгового кластера как инновационного фактора и его теоретические вопросы. Представлено состояние изучения понятия кластера зарубежными и отечественными учеными, а также некоторые взгляды на его определение. Исследованы теоретические вопросы кластеризации, впервые разработано и теоретически обосновано определение торгового кластера.*

Ключевые слова: *торговля, кластер, торговый кластер, материальные блага, товар, нематериальные блага, финансовый ресурс, деньги, торговый процесс, имущественные права.*

INTRODUCTION There is one truth in human history, when you don't have the strength to do something, you have to join forces. Today, we are capable of many things, but it is necessary to ensure faster development and increase competitiveness. Because in the worldThe COVID-19 pandemic that started in 2020had a negative impact on the economy of all countries. As a result of its influence, a significant decrease is observed in all sectors and sectors of the economy of the countries. In particular, the trade sector is facing several problems caused by the crisis. Now is the time to see a way out of this difficulty. A lot of organizational and economic activities are being carried out now. One of these causes the need to use the cluster mechanism in the economy.

In today's globalization, the whole world has been covered by the pandemic. In such circumstances, at the current stage of the development of the national economy, the organization of innovation-based clusters is of particular importance. In this regard, as the President noted, "If our Parliament ... adopts the new law "On Cooperation and Clusters" as soon as possible... an important legal basis for the future work in this field will be created in Uzbekistan." Yes, in order to implement something, it is necessary to organize its legal basis first.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results.Currently, despite the fact that the word cluster and related concepts are widely used in international practice and in a number of disciplines, including economics, the explanation of this word remains almost unexplained. In particular, this word is almost not used in the Uzbek language. In particular, in the 2-volume "Russian-Uzbek

dictionary" published in 1983 this word was not explained. The 5-volume "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" published in 2006 does not include this word and related concepts.

The cluster mechanism can be used in all areas. In this article, we found it appropriate to dwell on the content of the trade cluster. To carry out tasks related to the unification of forces in this area we aimed to use the important innovative directions of development of trade enterprises and the trade services provided in them on a modern basis in our country. One of them is the cluster method used in the field of trade. At this point, it is worth noting that we recommend calling it a cluster method from the point of view of managing the trade sector, and a cluster mechanism from the point of view of implementing the economic process. Because when one place is used in one place and the other is used in another place, we have shown it separately in order to understand which goal is intended.

Today, traditional methods and factors of economic development are not effective enough in the processes of saving the economy from various crises. In mitigating the negative consequences of the problems that have arisen under the conditions of the pandemic, the implementation of the "cluster" method based on innovative factors, thereby uniting several forces towards one goal, is the most reasonable way. The "Cluster" method is considered as a modern system that fully meets the requirements of national and regional development, increasing the competitiveness of enterprises based on the acceleration of innovative activities.

According to A. Marshal, one of the manifestations of the "cluster" theory, his opinion on the integration of specialized branches and industries in separate regions is the basis for the unification of several forces. According to his scientific conclusions, the regional integration of specialized entities is based on the availability of skilled labor resources, the growth of supply and additional industries, and the existence of specialization of various firms in various stages of the production process. M. Porter also noted that the company's success in the competition depends on the development of its relations with its partners and consumers.

According to Michael Porter, the founder of the idea of applying the cluster theory to the development of the competitiveness of countries and regions, a "cluster" is a group of geographically neighboring, interrelated companies (manufacturers, product suppliers, etc.) and organizations operating in a certain field, providing services related to them. (educational institutions, government agencies, infrastructural companies) is a group. Or "cluster" - communities that form a single technological chain of closely interconnected industries, creating opportunities for the growth of the competitiveness of production enterprises.

Based on the tariff given to the concept of cluster, today it is confirmed that one of the modern and main directions of increasing the competitiveness of enterprises is the cluster.

From the evolution of the "cluster" theory, two fundamental characteristics can be distinguished.

The first- the activities of the enterprises and firms integrated into the cluster must be related to the market of exactly the same type of goods. It should be related. Such a relationship can be vertical (buying and selling chain) or horizontal (use of additional departments and services, special costs, technologies or institutions and other connections).

The second- clusters are a group of interrelated enterprises located geographically close, and as a result of stabilization of mutual economic and social relations between them, development of competitiveness, creation of more added value and creation of opportunities for sale in the market.

As can be seen from the above comments, "Cluster theory" has entered the scientific process in the form of a marketing strategy, as a mechanism that ensures that the enterprises of the state, region and regions win in the competitive environment of the market. Because of this bToday, the study and use of cluster theory is growing rapidly in the world. The reason is that the implementation of the cluster is becoming one of the main directions of national economic and social development and increasing competitiveness based on mutual relations.

Now we want to focus directly on the development of the definition of the trade cluster. The sales process is also a multifaceted process that includes tangible, financial, and intangible activities and areas. Materiality, in the field of trade, goods and other material assets are sold directly. The financial movement in it becomes invisible in the way that in the process of trading of goods, money (financial resources) performs an equivalent function. Intangible benefits involved in the sales process can include the awakening of the customer's feeling for the goods, the effect of advertising, the excellence of the quality of the sales culture. All these processes should be reflected in the definition of the trade cluster. Based on these requirements, we can define the trade cluster as follows.

A trade cluster is a grouping of a number of interrelated persons and economic entities within a separate field for the effective implementation of the process of transfer of material, financial and immaterial benefits from one person to another person involved in the sales process.

The definition of a trade cluster can be theoretically explained as follows. First of all, this cluster reflects the sales process, which represents the implementation of sales. Because in the absence of a sale process, the change of ownership of material goods does not fall within the sphere of trade.

Secondly, the participation of tangible, financial and intangible benefits involved in the sales process was taken into account. Currently, the trade object sells not only goods and other material assets, but also intangible assets. After all, intangible assets also have a market and value.

Thirdly, in the process of trading, the ownership of the above-mentioned goods changes from one person to another. This is an important function of the trade sector and the services provided in it. Therefore, the presence of this condition in the definition of a trade cluster is an objective necessity.

Fourthly, the fact that a number of interrelated persons and economic entities unite within a separate field for effective implementation of the trade process as a whole is reflected in the definition, which indicates its high efficiency. Because all forces are combined to implement the trade and a chain of actions aimed at the realization of one goal is formed. This is one of the important features of the cluster.

In conclusion, the study of the trade cluster showed that the content of the trade cluster has not yet been fully revealed. Due to this, several conclusions were reached.

First of all, there are not enough researches on the understanding of the trade cluster as a modern innovative factor and on its theoretical issues, not only in our country, but also among the elites of the world.

Secondly, despite the use of the term cluster in foreign countries, we witnessed that it is not used enough in dictionaries and scientific literature in the CIS countries and in our country.

Thirdly, the theoretical issues related to the term cluster and its definition were studied, the definition of the term trade cluster was developed for the first time and this definition was theoretically justified.

In short, the application of these scientific recommendations to the theoretical part of economic sciences and practice, while showing that the concept related to the term cluster can be used in various sectors, also leads to the improvement of their aspects related to the field of trade. In the end, it will serve to reflect the priority tasks related to the use of cluster mechanisms carried out in the economic policy of our country in practice.

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